

LAW OF EVIDENCE SUBJECT IN A NUTSHELL: A LOOK INTO EXISTING COURSE OUTLINE OFFERED FOR THE LAW DEGREE PROGRAM IN THE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

Justice and evidence go hand in hand in the legal and judicial world, evidence often impacts and changes the game of legal suits in court. For law degree program, law of evidence subject is very important. All legal disputes whether in civil or criminal will require the submission of evidence. Without evidence, the parties to the legal disputes will unable to get favorable judgment for their case from the court. Due to its important, law of evidence subject has been made as a compulsory subject for law program offered by law school in the university. It is a must learn subject for every law student. Every jurisdiction has their own version of evidence rules including Malaysia. Being part of British colony for more than hundred years, the British has left their marks in the country legal system and this includes the law pertaining to evidence. In Malaysia, the country has the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] which regulates the submission of evidence to the court. The Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] defines evidence, admissibility of evidence, authentication process of evidence and the burden and standard of evidence. Ever since it was introduced during the British colonial era, many amendments have been made to the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] in order to make it relevant to the current legal and judicial needs. The law of evidence is part of adjectival law (the law of procedure in its widest sense) that regulates the proof of facts in court. The function of the law of evidence is to determine the admissibility and weight (by evaluation) of the fact and fact in issue. Evidence is the only possible way by which the court can make inferences to render a decision for a case which been presented to them. The definition of evidence explains that evidence is the proof of any fact and fact in issue so without evidence there will be no possibilities to prove any fact or fact in issues or even to establish any matter in the legal disputes. The process of evidencing should be governed by a well-established law in order to achieve speedy and fair justice. The law of evidence is not just a fundamental principle governing the process of proof rather it also has a multidimensional purpose of governing the rules relating to the process of proof in court proceedings. It is very crucial for the subject to be properly taught to the law students so that the students will have basic idea how law of evidence been regulated and applied in the country. Thus, it is the object of this paper to highlight the existing contents over law of evidence subject which been offered by law schools in the university. The researcher will also highlight any latest amendments which been made to the country main legislation which regulates the submission of evidence and the need for this latest amendment to be inserted into the existing course outline. It is very important for the course outlines on law of evidence subject be review and improve by highlighting the latest amendments in order to strengthen the offered course and the quality of students which undertaken the law program.

Keywords: Evidence, course, enhancement

1.0 INTRODUCTION

No one can deny the important of evidence. Evidence is a very important tool in order to determine the truth and to prevent false. (Mentor, 2020). The use of evidence is not limited in the court of law only. The daily life of every human is being surrounded with the need over evidence. A simple dispute on the streets or inside a restaurant or supermarket will require the use of evidence. The crucial need of evidence is also important for scientific community where every scientist will require producing evidence to prove any of their scientific discoveries. (Taper, Mark L.; Lele, Subhash, 2004). Those studying religion also need to produce evidence. (John W. Welch, 2011). The existence of God itself or to prove the divinity of the prophet will usually require the submission of evidence. In short, the need over evidence is endless. Every aspect of our life will require some use of evidence. The important of evidence become more crucial when it come to the court of law. Litigation, by its very nature, is adversarial. It pits two or more parties against each other in a legal forum to resolve a dispute. But how does a judge or jury determine which party is in the right? This is where the concept of evidence becomes essential. Evidence forms the cornerstone of any litigation case, serving as the compass that guides the court to its final decision. At its core, evidence provides the court with a factual basis upon which to decide. Without evidence, the court would have to rely on mere allegations, conjectures, or even biases, making the justice system vulnerable to manipulation. In the grand theater of litigation, evidence is both the script and the stage. It provides the narrative that the court follows, guiding it towards a just and fair conclusion. (Litigation Lawyer Services, 2023).

Whatever allegation or accusation we might have towards anyone, it must be supported with an evidence. People need to be aware the consequence over their baseless allegation or accusation towards anyone. Without evidence, the accuser can be subjected to legal action either for slander or defamation from the victim. (Legal Advice). Thus, it is very important for an allegation or accusation to be substantiated with evidence. People cannot simply allege or accuse anyone doing anything or say something improper or against the law without any evidence. We must never tolerate the culture of a making wild allegation or false accusation without the existence of evidence. There is long list of negative impact for making baseless allegation or accusation, from destroying victim reputation until creating major chaos in the society.

People need to be educated over the need to submit evidence for any allegation or accusation they might have. The need for evidence becomes more vital when we want to bring a case in court. In law, evidence refers to information that the plaintiff, prosecutor or defendant presents to the court in order for the court to rule in his or her favor. The requirement to have strong evidence to support any particular case not only arises due to ensure justice and fairness in any court proceeding, but also because of common sense and logic. (Haswira Nor Mohamad Hashim and Anida Mahmood, 2009, pp: 98 – 121). Without having strong evidence, it would be difficult to uphold justice and fairness. Without having in place strong evidence support any particular case, it would also difficult to uphold rule of law and it would also difficult to administer the existing legal system. (A.K. Sarkar and S.K. Awasthi, 1996, pp: 160 – 161). The important of justice and fairness has become the most important point in Islamic legal system. There have been many verses in the Holy Qur'an as well as the saying of the Holy Prophet Muhammad SAW which emphasis on the important of justice and fairness in daily aspect of life including when settling any dispute between parties. (Mahmud Saedon A. Othman, 2000, pp. 1 – 14 and Afzalur Rahman, 1995, pp: 347 – 356).

When it's come to the submission of evidence in court, every country which practice democracy and uphold the rule of law already have some mechanism in place in order to submit evidence to their respective court. In Malaysia, the submission of evidence is governed by the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56]. By virtue of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56], there are many varieties of evidence which can be used to substantiate any allegation in the court of law like oral testimony from a witness, documentary evidence, circumstantial evidence, physical evidence and many more. Section 3 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] states evidence includes: (a) all statements which the court permits or requires to be made before it by witnesses in relation to matters of fact under inquiry: such statements are called oral evidence; (b) all documents produced for the inspection of the court: such documents are called documentary evidence. The use of the word "includes" in this particular section is intended to make the definition of evidence in the section extensive and not being confined to the submission of oral and documentary evidence only. This means that the meaning of the word evidence in the section goes beyond the narrow statutory meaning explicitly set out. This view is based in the case of *Chin Seow Noi v PP* [1994] 1 SLR 135 where Yong Pung How CJ said at page 156 "The use of the

single word 'includes' in our s 3 is clearly intended to make the definition of 'evidence' in our Evidence Act an extensive one". Similar view also been taken in the following case of *Noliana Sulaiman v PP* [2001] 1 CLJ 36, *Dilworth & Ors v Commissioner of Stamps* [1899] AC 99, *Corporation of Portsmouth v Smith & Ors*. (1883) 13 QBD 184 and many more.

Thus, there are varieties of evidence which can be used to substantiate any allegation or accusation in both civil and criminal proceeding like oral evidence, documentary evidence, physical evidence and circumstantial evidence. Based on the above discussion, it is clear to us that evidence is very important element in order to support any allegation or accusation made towards anyone. Absence of evidence can essentially put an end to a person's legal claim. Evidence can take many forms and it helps the judge determine that one or the other party has proven the elements of his or her case. If one party does not have evidence to back up the things he or she said in the court, then the court must not side in his or her favor. The need for evidence is part and parcel to uphold justice and to do fairness toward everyone.

When discussing about evidence and the rule of law, everybody also needs to respect one of the most sacred principles in any legal justice system which holds that a defendant or accused is innocent until been proven guilty by the court of the competent jurisdiction. This gives rise to the presumption of innocence. Until the case properly been proven and final judgement is delivered by the court of competent jurisdiction, it must be known that one is considered innocence unless proven otherwise. This is in line with the latin maxim *ei incumbit probatio qui dicit, non qui negat* which means the burden of proof is on the one who declares, not on one who denies. The phrase is a legal maxim in criminal law relevant to the presumption of innocence and indicates the legal burden of proof falls upon the prosecution making the charge and not the defendant. Based on this Latin maxim, the prosecution has the duty to prove their case against the defendant or accused. If the case unable to be prove, then the defendant or accused entitle to be acquitted from the crime which been charge. Until final verdict is given by the court, it is better for everyone to observe and respect the presumption of innocence principle. This presumption also applied similarly in civil cases. Basically, there are two sets of standard or quantum of proof which need to be satisfied before the defendant or accused can be found guilty and faced legal sentence namely balance of probabilities which been adopted in civil trial and beyond a reasonable doubt for criminal trial. Reference can be made to the case of *Sinnaiyah & Sons Sdn Bhd v Damai Setia Sdn Bhd* [2015] 5 MLJ for this point. Until the case properly been proven and final judgement is delivered by the court of competent jurisdiction, it must be known that one is considered innocence unless proven otherwise. Thus, the submission of evidence is very vital to build a case in the court.

As such, it is importance to uphold such presumption of innocence principle in order to avoid any unfair treatment or negative perception been given to defendant or accused before the trial has ended and final decision been given. Such presumption of innocence is a legal belonging to all accused in a court trial and it also been consider as part of human rights which clearly been guaranteed under Article 11 of the UN's Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948 (UDHR 1948). Article 11 (1) of UDHR 1948 states that "Everyone charged with a penal offence has the right to be presumed innocent until proved guilty according to law in a public trial at which he has had all the guarantees necessary for his defence". The presumption of innocence is a basic right conferred upon an accused by the common law of England as stated in the case of *Woolmington v DPP* [1935] AC 462.

In Malaysia, though our Federal Constitution did not specifically mentioned presumption of innocence but through many decided court cases, it clearly showed that such principle has been existed, respected and adopted in our country. A simple reference on this matter can be made to the Federal Court case of *PP v Gan Boon Aun* [2017] 4 CLJ 41. Such right can also be seen given through Article 5 (1) of the Malaysian Federal Constitution. Article 5 of the Malaysian Federal Constitution enshrines a number of basic fundamental human rights on individual life and liberty. Article 5 (1) states that "No person in the country may be deprived of life or personal liberty except in accordance with law". This universal presumption of innocence should be extended to those who are undergoing an appeal process. We should allow those undergoing appeal processes to proceed with their case until a final decision been given by the highest court in the land. It is an established principle in Malaysian jurisprudence that an appeal is a continuation of a trial. (Salleh Buang, 2022). That principle was first recognised in the case of *Balasingham v Public Prosecutor* [1959] 1 MLJ 193 and has since been followed and endorsed, including in the Federal Court in the recent case of *Bird Dominic Jude v Public Prosecutor* [2014] 3 MLJ 745. In this case, the Federal Court explained that during an appeal, the criminal proceedings against the appellant are continued. If an appeal process is regarded as a continuation of trial and the presumption of innocence is regarded as a fundamental right in a

criminal trial, there is no reasonable or even lawful justification to deny a convicted person of this right during the appeal process. As such, it is importance to continue uphold presumption of innocence principle in order to avoid any unfair treatment or negative perception been given to defendant or accused before the trial or appeal process has ended.

2.0 THE MALAYSIAN EVIDENCE ACT 1950 [ACT 56]

The law of Malaysia is mainly based on the common law legal system. This was a direct result of the colonization of Malaya (Peninsular Malaysia), Sarawak, and North Borneo (Now Sabah) by Britain between the early 19th century to the 1960s. (Wu Min Aun, 1997, pp: 1 – 41). The supreme law of the land is the Federal Constitution. As the highest law in the country, the Federal Constitution sets out the legal framework and rights of Malaysian citizens. There are basically three sources of Malaysian law namely written law, unwritten law and Muslim law. (Lee Mei Pheng, 1997, pp: 13 – 47). There are several laws which operate in the country. Federal laws enacted by the Parliament of Malaysia apply throughout the country. There are also state laws enacted by the State Legislative Assemblies which applies in the particular state. The Federal Constitution also provides for a unique dual justice system namely the man-made laws (criminal and civil) and Syariah laws. Due to these unique dual justice systems, the county also has two set of judicial avenues namely the Civil Court and the Syariah Court Unlike Saudi Arabia which effectively equates Syariah law to national law, Malaysia only partially implements the system. Syariah law in Malaysia applies only to restricted areas of personal and family law, such as marriage and custody-and only to Muslims. Article 121 (1A) of the Federal Constitution gives exclusive jurisdiction to the Syariah Courts in the administration of Islamic laws. (Ashgar Ali Ali Mohamed (Ed.), 2014, pp: 319 – 349). However, despite having Islam as its official religion, Malaysia is not strictly an Islamic state as it allows other religions to be practiced within it in peace and harmony. Most of the Malaysian law is a man-made or secular civil law derived from the British common law system. Often, English legislation and case law still apply, as legacies of colonialism that remain in many former British colonies. (Victoria Soh, 2020). The application of English law or common law is specified in statutes. Section 5 of Criminal Procedure Code [Act 593] states that English law shall be applied in cases where no specific legislation has been enacted. Similarly, in context of civil law, Sections 3 and 5 of Civil Law Act [Act 67] allows for application of English common law, equity rules, and statutes in Malaysian civil cases where no specific laws have been made.

The effect of having these unique dual justice systems can also be seen in the evidence matter. As for civil court, the submission of evidence is regulated under the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56]. Section 2 of Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] states that “This Act shall apply to all judicial proceedings in or before any court, but not to affidavits presented to any court or officers, nor to proceedings before an arbitrator”. This means that Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] regulates the submission of evidence for civil and criminal proceeding in the country. Reference can be made to the following case of *Saminathan v PP* [1955] MLJ 121, *Re Loh Kah Kheng* (1990) 2 MLJ 126, *Malaysia Building Society Bhd v Univein Sdn Bhd* [2003] 5 MLJ 394, *Far East Holdings Bhd & Anor v Majlis Ugama Islam and Adat Resam Melayu Pahang and other appeals* [2018] 1 MLJ 1 and many more. The word “court” under Section 2 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] means a court established by or under Part IX of the Federal Constitution which includes a judge, a Sessions Court judge, a Magistrate, and every person legally authorized to take evidence (Except for arbitrator). Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] does not apply to Domestic Inquiry, Tribunals, Industrial Court and Syariah Court. Examples of Tribunals include Tribunal for Consumer Claims, Tribunal for Homebuyers Claims, and Copyright Tribunal. The exclusion of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] from the Syariah Court can also be seen under Section 131 of the Syariah Court Evidence Act (FT) 1997 [Act 561] which clearly states “With the coming into operation of this Act (i.e The Syariah Court Evidence Act), the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] shall not be applicable to the Court. (i.e. Syariah Court)”. The Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] is modeled and based on the Indian Evidence Act of 1872 [Act No. 1 of 1872] drafted by Sir James Stephen. The Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] is modeled on the Indian Evidence Act which is a codified form of English Law. Per Thomson CJ (as he then was) in *Looi Wooi Saik v PP* [1962] MLJ 337, 339 (CA) stated “In this country the question is governed by the terms of the Evidence Ordinance which is the same as the Indian Evidence Act...It is generally accepted that the Indian Act was drafted by Sir James Stephen in 1872 with the intention of stating in a codified form of English law relating to evidence as it stood at that date”. The Indian Evidence Act 1872 [Act No. 1 of 1872] which also is based on the English law of evidence in the late 19TH century with certain modifications, which were made to suit the local circumstances in India. As result of several amendments, the local Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] has certain provisions which are not found in the Indian Evidence Act 1872 [Act No. 1 of 1872]. The Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] has 167 sections which covered various aspect over submission of evidence in the Malaysian court. Generally, the Malaysian

Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] embodied aspects over the definition as well as types of evidence as well as the method of authenticity of such evidence. (Augustine Paul, 2000, pp. 1 – 13).

3.0 AMENDMENTS MADE TO THE MALAYSIAN EVIDENCE ACT 1950 [ACT 56]

Law, particularly man-made law is always subject to changes. Changes are need so that it could adapt with the surrounding changes which happen in the society. Similar with other statutes, Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] also has been subjected to several changes in the past until present. The most notable changes made to the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] was the insertion of 'Computer Generated Document' evidence part under Section 90A, 90B and 90C of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56]. Malaysia amended its statute on evidence in 1993 to incorporate a section on electronic evidence which is also known as 'Computer Generated Document' evidence. This update in the law came rather later than those in fellow Commonwealth countries such as Australia and the United Kingdom, where most additions to current law dealing with technology were incorporated in the 1970s and 1980s. Nevertheless, Section 90A of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] is what governs Malaysia in terms of electronic or digital evidence and its admissibility. The words 'electronic evidence', 'digital evidence', 'computer generated evidence' and several other similar terms are used interchangeably. However, they all refer to the same legal definition in the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] basically "a document produced by a computer". The reason Malaysian Parliament incorporated this section into the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] is because they wanted to bring the law up to date with the realities of technology. What is a computer? When most people think of a computer, they think of a desktop or laptop, but the legal definition in the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] is again very wide. The Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] defines a computer as a device that performs 'logical, arithmetic, storage and display functions, and includes any data storage facility or communications facility'. Under the law, a computer can include a ticket vending machine and a smartphone. Judicial interpretations of 'document produced by a computer' have included bank statements, lists of car registrations from the department of motor vehicles and computerised results of DNA profiling and caller or SMS ID reports. Reference can be made to the following case namely PP v Azilah Hadri [2015] 1 CLJ 579, (the Altantuya murder trial) and Pathmanabhan Nalliannen v PP [2017] 4 CLJ 137 (the Sosilawati murder trial). (Anushia Kandasivam, 2016). To submit this type of document, certain conditions must be satisfied. These conditions can be found under Section 90A of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56].

Section 90A (1) of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] states "In any criminal or civil proceeding a document produced by a computer, or a statement contained in such document, shall be admissible as evidence of any fact stated therein if the document was produced by the computer in the course of its ordinary use, whether or not the person tendering the same is the maker of such document or statement. (2) For the purposes of this section it may be proved that a document was produced by a computer in the course of its ordinary use by tendering to the court a certificate signed by a person who either before or after the production of the document by the computer is responsible for the management of the operation of that computer, or for the conduct of the activities for which that computer was used. (3) (a) It shall be sufficient, in a certificate given under subsection (2), for a matter to be stated to the best of the knowledge and belief of the person stating it. (b) A certificate given under subsection (2) shall be admissible in evidence as prima facie proof of all matters stated in it without proof of signature of the person who gave the certificate. (4) Where a certificate is given under subsection (2), it shall be presumed that the computer referred to in the certificate was in good working order and was operating properly in all respects throughout the material part of the period during which the document was produced. (5) A document shall be deemed to have been produced by a computer whether it was produced by it directly or by means of any appropriate equipment, and whether or not there was any direct or indirect human intervention. (6) A document produced by a computer, or a statement contained in such document, shall be admissible in evidence whether or not it was produced by the computer after the commencement of the criminal or civil proceeding or after the commencement of any investigation or inquiry in relation to the criminal or civil proceeding or such investigation or inquiry, and any document so produced by a computer shall be deemed to be produced by the computer in the course of its ordinary use. (7) Notwithstanding anything contained in this section, a document produced by a computer, or a statement contained in such document, shall not be admissible in evidence in any criminal proceeding, where it is given in evidence by or on behalf of the person who is charged with an offence in such proceeding the person so charged with the offence being a person who was—(a) responsible for the management of the operation of that computer or for the conduct of the activities for which that computer was used; or (b) in any manner or to any extent involved, directly or indirectly, in the production of the document by the computer". From this section it is clear to us that in order to submit this type of evidence there are several basic conditions which need to be fulfil namely first, by law it is a document produced by a computer. Second, this definition covers

almost everything. Third, for it to be admissible in court, there needs to be a certificate drafted by someone with knowledge of how the document was produced or the person with knowledge of how it was produced should come to court to explain how it was produced.

Another amendment which was made to the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] is the introduction of Section 114A in 2012. This section states that “(1) A person whose name, photograph or pseudonym appears on any publication depicting himself as the owner, host, administrator, editor or sub-editor, or who in any manner facilitates to publish or re-publish the publication is presumed to have published or re-published the contents of the publication unless the contrary is proved. (2) A person who is registered with a network service provider as a subscriber of a network service on which any publication originates from is presumed to be the person who published or re-published the publication unless the contrary is proved. (3) Any person who has in his custody or control any computer on which any publication originates from is presumed to have published or re-published the content of the publication unless the contrary is proved. (4) For the purpose of this section- (a) “network service” and “network service provider” have the meaning assigned to them in section 6 of the Communications and Multimedia Act 1998 [Act 588]; and (b) “publication” means a statement or a representation, whether in written, printed, pictorial, film, graphical, acoustic or other form displayed on the screen of a computer”. This amendment significantly impacts the law governing internet publications by persons in Malaysia, including news reporting, blogging and interactions in social media. The amendment will allow the prosecution or a plaintiff to rely on a presumption of fact to prove the identity of the person responsible for an internet publication. Essentially, the internet user identified under Section 114A is deemed to be the publisher of the content, unless the internet user proves otherwise. Hence, the burden of proof has shifted. This amendment to the law of evidence in Malaysia has far-reaching consequences for internet users. It will facilitate proving offences under the Communications and Multimedia Act 1998 [Act 588], the Computer Crimes Act 1997 [Act 563] and the Sedition Act 1948 [Act 15] against internet users. It will also ease proving defamation claims based on online publications. While the Malaysian government has defended the amendment as being necessary to protect the public interest, the internet community in Malaysia has reacted with an uproar. Section 114A is a presumption of fact and not a presumption of law. (Pauline Lim Wenjun, 2019). And that is why it is crafted, drafted and inserted into the Evidence Act. That means, it is only for evidence purposes not creating another offence.

On 29 March 2023, the Malaysian Parliament through Dewan Rakyat (House of Representatives) has passed by voice vote the amendment Bill of the Evidence of Child Witness Act 2007 [Act 676] after its third reading. (Soo Wern Jun, 2023). Insertion of Section 6A into the above Act provide special hearings whereby the testimony of a child witness can be taken in the form of a video recording so children do not have to attend the trial thus avoiding the trauma of facing the abuser in court. The age limit of child witness has also been increased from 16 to 18 years so that it is in line with Child Act 2001 [Act 611]. Section 6A provide for special hearing which states: (1) Where the Court directs that evidence of a child witness be given by way of a special hearing, the Court may determine the time and place where the special hearing shall be conducted and the persons who may be present during the special hearing (2) During the special hearing, a child witness shall be first examined-in-chief by the party to the proceedings who calls him, then, if the adverse party so desires, cross-examined then, if the party calling the child witness so desires, re-examined (3) Where the evidence of a child witness has been given by way of a special hearing, the child witness shall not be recalled for further examination-in-chief, cross-examination or re-examination in the proceedings of the case unless the Court is satisfied that—(a) the examination is sought by a party to the proceedings as a result of that party having become aware, since the time when the evidence was recorded, of a matter which that party could not with reasonable diligence have ascertained by then; or (b) it is in the interest of justice to permit further examination of the child witness if his evidence appears to the Court essential to the just decision of the case (4) A child witness during a special hearing may give evidence by means of having a screen between him and the accused or child charged with any offence or by means of a live link or combination of both and (5) For the purposes of this section, the Court may, where necessary, give any direction on any other matters relating to a special hearing as the Court considers appropriate. The Bill also included amendments to Clause 6B (1) which reads, “The Court shall prohibit any improper question to the child witness which appears to the Court to be — misleading or confusing; insulting, intimidating, humiliating, harassing, annoying, offensive, oppressive or needlessly repetitive; belittling in its manner or tone or otherwise inappropriate; or of no basis other than a stereotype based on the child witness’ sex, race, culture or ethnicity, age or disability. For the purpose of subsection (1), the Court may have regards to the age, maturity, vulnerability or disability of the child witness as well as cultural background or religious beliefs of the child witness.

4.0 CONCLUSION

It is very important for Law of Evidence course which been offered in all law schools in the country to re-evaluate their course outlines and inserted all the amendments made to the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] in recent years. This is to ensure the students able to update themselves with all the amendments made to the statute and be fully prepared when they started to do their practice after finish with their study. The course outlines must also be equipped with all the latest cases so that students will able to understand the latest court decision or opinion on any provisions which touch on evidence.

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